

control because of increased leaf area, chlorophyll content, and grains/panicle, and had slender grains. Growth duration,

however, was 10 days longer.

The mutants were photosynthetically efficient and the induced dwarfism in

these mutants increased yields. They are being tested for direct use and as parents to provide alternative dwarfing sources. □

Performance of TKM6 and its mutants for different traits. ^a

Mutants	Duration (days)	Height (cm)	Productive tillers (no.)	Leaf area (cm ²)	Chlorophyll (mg/g)		Grains per panicle	Length-breadth ratio of grain	Productivity per day (kg/ha)	Total dry matter productivity/plant (g)	Harvest index
					'a'	'b'					
TKM6 control	120	120.0	8	17.89	0.715	0.328	110	3.00	37.50	30.0	30.00
TKM6 30 kR D ₁	110	70.0 (-41.6)	7	14.49 (-19.0)	1.009 (+41.0)	0.586 (+78.8)	145 (+31.8)	1.73	45.45 (+21.20)	17.95 (-40.16)	55.71
TKM6 35 + 30	120	116.0 (-5)	11	21.73 (+21.4)	1.043 (+45.8)	0.480 (+46.2)	135 (+22.7)	3.40	58.33 (+55.54)	41.00 (+36.66)	34.15
TKM6 35 kR D ₃	130	75.0 (-37.5)	10	19.14 (+ 6.9)	1.006 (+40.5)	0.597 (+82.0)	165 (+50.0)	3.30	61.54 (+64.08)	37.50 (+25.0)	42.67

^aFigures in parentheses indicate percentage increase or decrease over control.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Inheritance of blast *Pyricularia oryzae* resistance in rice.

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We sought to determine the number of leaf blast resistance genes present in some rice breeding lines and varieties, based on the presence or absence of lesions on F₁ and F₂ populations. The F₁s and segregating populations were inoculated with several races of the pathogen by injection. This study was conducted at IRRI in 1979 and 1980.

Lines derived from Tetep/IR8 (IR1905-81-3-1, IR3259-PP5-160-1, and IR3259-PP8-172-7) were resistant to six blast isolates and the Taiwanese variety Pai-kan-tao was resistant to three (see table). None of the varieties were resistant to an isolate from large lesions on Tetep. IR442-2-58, IR8, Peta, and Nongbaek were susceptible to all seven isolates. Among parents resistant to the same isolate, different genes controlled resistance. Also, for a given parent, dif-

Number of genes resistant to specific isolates of the blast fungus, identified in three breeding lines and one variety.

Line, variety	Fungus race	Resistance genes (no.)	Gene interaction
IR1905-81-3-la	IB45	2	Complementary
	ID-15	2	Complementary
	ID-16	1	Dominant
	IH-1(43+PO7-10) ^b	1+1	Dominant
	II-1	1	Dominant
IR3259-PP5-160-1 ^a	IB-45	2	Complementary
	ID-15	2	Complementary
	ID-16	1	Dominant
	IH-1(43+PO7-10) ^b	1+1	Dominant
	II-1	1	Dominant
IR3259-PP8-172-7 ^c	IB-45	2	Complementary
	ID-15	2	Complementary
	ID-16	2	Complementary
	IH-1 (43+PO7-10) ^b	1+1	Dominant
	II-1	1	Dominant
Pai-kan-tao ^d	IH-1 (43+PO7-10) ^b	2+2	Complementary
	II-1	2	Duplicate

^a In this line, the genes resistant to the races studied appear to be the same or allelic. ^b Isolates 43 and PO7-10 were differentiated as race IH-1 but distinct genes controlled resistance to each of them.

^c The resistance genes in this line are apparently the same or allelic to those in IR905-81-3-1 and IR3259-PP5-160-1 except for race ID-16. ^d Genes for resistance detected in this variety were non-allelic to the corresponding genes in IR905-81-3-1, IR3259-PP5-160-1, and IR3259-PP8-172-7.

ferent genes controlled resistance to different races.

Apparently, several blast resistance genes are available in a single genotype. Different genes control resistance to a particular race in different genotypes—

the genes in Pai-kan-tao that govern resistance to race IH-1 (isolates PO7-10 and 43) and II-1 are different from those in IR81905-81-3-1, IR3259-PP5-160-1, and IR3259-PP8-172-7. No complementary recessive genes for resistance were

detected in the F₂ of crosses among susceptible parents.

Of the eight resistance genes found in IR1905-81-3-1 and IR3259-PP5-160-1, and nine genes in IR3259-PP8-172-7, the

gene conferring resistance to race IH-1 (isolate PO7-10) seems to be linked to the gene resistant to race II-1. The two genes giving resistance to race IB-45 did not segregate independently from the two

genes resistant to race ID-15 or from that acting against race IH-1 (isolate 43); the remaining genes showed no linkage. The six resistance genes in Pai-kan-tao segregated independently. □

Resistance of five IR varieties to tungro

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IR36, IR42, IR50, IR54, and IR56 resistance to tungro was determined by mass screening and test tube inoculation methods.

The five IR varieties and TN1 (susceptible check) were inoculated in a cage with 1, 3, and 4 insects/seedling using the tungro mass screening method. Seedling infection increased as insects increased from 1 to 5/seedling (see figure). TN1 always had the highest percentage of infection, regardless of the number of insects per seedling; followed by IR42, IR36, IR56, and IR50. IR54 showed the lowest seedling infection, but infection level was not significantly different from that of IR50 and IR56.

By the reaction scale for tungro, IR36 and IR42 changed their reaction from resistant to susceptible when the number of insects per seedling was increased from 1 to 5. IR50, IR54, and IR56 reaction changed from resistant to intermediate (see table).

Seven-day-old seedlings were each inoculated with 1, 3, and 5 insects, using the test tube inoculation method. Again, percentage of infected seedlings increased with number of insects per seedling (see figure). However, at even 1 insect/seedling, IR36, IR42, and TN1 were susceptible. IR50, IR54, and IR56 had an intermediate reaction (see table). The highest percentage of infection using the test tube inoculation method, regardless of number of insects, may be caused by the insects' forced feeding on the seedling in confinement.

These results indicate possible unstable tungro resistance in some IR varieties. In the field, degree of resistance decreases with increased disease and insect pressure. This is apparent on varieties with tungro resistance conditioned only by resistance to the vector insect.

Seedling infection (%)

Percentage seedling infection of 5 tungro-resistant IR varieties inoculated with different numbers of tungro-viruliferous *N. virescens* per seedling, following the mass screening and test tube methods of inoculation.

Tungro reaction of 5 IR varieties inoculated by 1, 3, or 5 insects per seedling, following the mass screening and test tube methods of inoculation.^a

Variety	Mass screening			Test tube inoculation		
	1	3	5	1	3	5
IR36	R	I	S	S	S	S
IR42	R	I	S	S	S	S
IR50	R	I	I	I	I	S
IR54	R	R	I	I	I	S
IR56	R	I	I	I	I	S
TN1	I	S	S	S	S	S

^aBased on the scale for RTV mass screening of resistant (R) = 0-30% seedling infection, intermediate (I) = 31-60% seedling infection, susceptible (S) = 61-100% seedling infection.

Reaction of rice varieties to blast and brown spot diseases at Ponnampet

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An experiment at the Ponnampet Agricultural Research Station, during 1982 kharif identified varieties resistant to

blast and brown spot diseases. The National Screening Nursery evaluated 334 entries under nursery and transplanted condition. The nursery followed the uniform blast nursery pattern.

Twenty-eight entries had resistance to blast and brown spot (Table 1). Seventy-eight were resistant to leaf blast 83 to neck blast, and 223 to brown spot (Table 2). □